

The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development

Report on Results and
Lessons Learned From
the Second Phase of
the Indicator Pilot

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Introduction

By mandate of the Ministers and High Authorities of Sport of Ibero-America, in 2022, the Ibero-American Council of Sport (CID), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), and the German Development Cooperation – GIZ, formed a consortium to develop the first common indicators to measure the impact of sport and physical activity on sustainable development in the Ibero-American region. Subsequently, in 2023, the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF) and the Rey Juan Carlos University of Spain joined the consortium.

The Ibero-American sport indicators aim to provide countries with regular, standardised and comparable information on the impact of sport on the various dimensions of sustainable development, as well as the periodic evaluation of policies that allows for the identification of opportunities for improvement and the support of achievements and results. Additionally, the indicators seek to facilitate the measurement of the social return on sport, ultimately encouraging increased investment in sport and physical activity. At the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, in May 2023, the unanimous approval was given for the creation of 12 indicators and four key data points to be implemented across the region. Furthermore, it was agreed to conduct a pilot implementation of these indicators in a group of applicant countries.

The objective of the pilot study was to validate the relevance and applicability of the indicators so that they may be scaled up to the entire region, as well as to carry out an initial calculation of those for which data is available according to existing information sources. Based on this, a report would be produced for each country on the status of the indicators, along with a cross-cutting document outlining the results and lessons learned.

A first phase of the pilot was conducted in Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador between August 2023 and March 2024, and its results were presented at the XXX General Assembly of the CID in Washington, D.C. A second phase of the pilot was implemented in Colombia and Peru between September 2024 and March 2025, and its results are expected to be presented at the XXXI General Assembly of the CID.

This document corresponds to the Results and Lessons Learned Report of the Phase Two Pilot. The Report aims to systematize the overall results of the pilot implementation, the technical assessment of the indicators by the countries, and the identification of the main lessons learned and recommendations.

The analysis and content of the Report are complemented by the Country Reports of each of the participating countries in the pilot program, as well as by the technical data sheets for the indicators. The country reports detail the specific context and challenges for each country in calculating the indicators, while the data sheets outline the technical procedures for their calculation.

The main message from the Results and Lessons Learned Report is that the objective of the Phase Two pilot program was successfully met by implementing all four key data points in the two participating countries, eight out of twelve indicators in Colombia, and four out of twelve indicators in Peru. Additionally, the countries successfully validated the technical attributes of the indicators and identified significant operational and administrative challenges that, taken together, will allow for improvements in the overall implementation of the pilot program throughout the region.

The level of indicator implementation in Phase Two of the pilot program was very similar to that achieved by the participating countries in Phase One. However, Phase Two was completed in three months (including training) compared to the seven months required for Phase One. This situation can be interpreted as a significant improvement in the organization, methodology, and training of the work

teams for the second phase. However, it is also important to note that the first phase of the pilot was carried out in three countries, while only two participated in the second.

Regarding the technical assessment of the indicators by the countries' technical teams, based on the attributes of clarity, feasibility, relevance, and cost-effectiveness, a very good rating was generally obtained, although the feasibility attribute scored lower. This was because calculating some indicators requires generating new sources of information, such as national surveys, satellite accounts, or administrative records, which implies the need for new budgetary resources in the countries.

One of the most important lessons learned during this phase is that more work from specialized technical teams is required to achieve strictly comparable indicators across countries. Currently, due to the different budget categories used by the countries and the diverse target populations of the national surveys, some indicators are not strictly comparable unless a more in-depth and rigorous conceptual and statistical standardization exercise is carried out by specialized technical teams. This can be done with the consortium's technical team, but it would require more time than is currently available for implementing the pilot.

Finally, it is important that the political commitment of the countries can be translated into concrete actions to strengthen their technical teams and compliance with the deadlines established in the pilot, which can be achieved through a closer and more institutional link between the Consortium and the High Authorities of the countries.

I. Systematization of results and status of the indicators achieved

The overall results of the Phase 2 pilot implementation in Colombia and Peru can be summarized in the following points:

Colombia:

- Of the four key data points, four were implemented (100% implementation).
- Of the 12 indicators, eight were implemented (66.6% implementation).

Peru:

- Of the four key data points, four were implemented (100% implementation).
- Of the 12 indicators, four were implemented (33.3% implementation).

The systematization of the results for each key data point is described in Table 1. With the exception of data point two, the possible response values for the remaining three data points were: “No,” “Partially,” and “Yes.” (CID, 2025). As can be seen, of the three data points with these characteristics, Colombia only has one with a “Yes” value, and Peru has none. Given that the desirable value of the three data points is “Yes”, there are significant challenges for countries to improve their institutional capacities in order to enhance the value of the data.

Table 1. Results of implementation of key data and indicators from the pilot

Name of the key data	Value of key data or indicator	
	Colombia	Peru
Key Data Point	Value	
1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	Partially
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Ministry	Autonomous body attached to the Ministry of Education
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	Partially
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Yes	Partially

Regarding the specific results of the indicators, these are presented in Table 2. A key initial observation about the indicators for Colombia and Peru is that some of them differ slightly from the generic wording of the indicator (first column) and are not strictly comparable between the countries (non-comparable indicators are marked in gray).

More specifically, the lack of comparability of the “Percentage of the public budget allocated to the national entity for sport and physical activity” is due to the fact that countries use different institutional and administrative arrangements to organize and execute their national budgets. Thus, some execute it to a greater extent from the central government and others from regional and local governments, although it was not possible to establish these exact proportions for both countries. In this sense, the very low percentage for Peru may be due to the fact that a considerable part of the national budget is executed by local and regional governments, unlike in Colombia, which most likely has a more centralized budget.

Indicators three and nine, related to the percentage of the sufficiently active population, are not strictly comparable because the countries use different target populations: Colombia uses the population aged 18 to 64, while Peru uses the population over 14 years of age. To achieve an exact comparison of the indicators, a statistical standardization exercise would be necessary, or surveys with the same design and target population would need to be created. These aspects are beyond the scope of this pilot study but will be necessary in the future to ensure the accuracy and international comparability of the indicators.

Finally, indicator eight, on “Percentage of women in management positions in the national sports entity,” is not strictly comparable because the countries use different definitions to establish management positions. Despite this limitation, the indicator provides a good measure for international comparison between countries on this topic.

Table 2. Results of pilot indicator implementation

Generic Name of the Indicator	Colombia		Peru	
	Name of the Indicator	Value	Name of the Indicator	Value
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity.	1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity disaggregated by function.	0.27%	1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity.	0.08%
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	2 Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	0.25%	2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	-
3. Percentage of the population sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age.	3. Percentage of the population from 18 to 64 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age.	51.3%	3. Percentage of the population over 14 years old sufficiently physically active.	42.0%
4 Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity.	4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	12.1%	4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	8.8%
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	-	5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	-
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	6. Percentage of school students (6-12 years old) sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	31.1%	6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	-

7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	-	7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	-
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	36.4%	8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	22.0%
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old	9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population from 18 to 64 years old	30.1%	9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old	-
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	2.7%	10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	-
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	-	11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	-
12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	-	12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	-

In general terms, the degree of implementation of the indicators is associated, firstly, with the availability of information sources and, secondly, with the countries' technical and operational capacity to carry out the pilot within the established timeframe.

It is important to note that for Phase 2 of the Pilot, the Consortium's technical team was strengthened by the addition of two specialists from Rey Juan Carlos University, who provided technological support and specialized monitoring and assistance to the Peruvian technical team for the development of indicators three and four. This primarily resulted in Peru being able to implement four indicators instead of just two.

On the other hand, the pilot project revealed that Colombia's technical team was larger and more interdisciplinary, which allowed it to move more quickly in calculating the indicators and providing more accurate and reliable sources of information. Similarly, even though both countries received the same type of training, Peru required more feedback than Colombia, which could be related to the fact that the Colombian team was better coordinated and had greater technical capabilities for developing the pilot. Additionally, Peru faced greater technological limitations in working with online documents, which translated into a need for more support from the technical team for managing and preparing the Country Report.

II. Technical Assessment of Key Data and Indicators

The technical assessment of key indicators and data refers to the assessment of certain basic criteria or attributes of the indicators by the countries' technical teams. The attributes evaluated and their definitions are as follows (for more information, see CID, 2025¹):

- *Clarity*: A key indicator or data point is clear when there is no doubt about what it is intended to measure. That is, the indicator's name is self-explanatory and consistent with the calculation method and the variables required for its calculation.
- *Feasibility*: A key indicator or data point is feasible when the calculation method and information sources are such that the indicator can be estimated with the available human, financial, material, and information resources, or, failing that, in the absence of such resources, that the effort required to achieve it does not represent an extraordinary undertaking.
- *Thematic relevance*: A key indicator or data point is thematically relevant when it provides effective information on a higher-level topic or strategic objective of policies for sport, physical activity, or physical education.
- *Cost-effectiveness*: A key indicator or data point is cost-effective if the benefit of generating the information for its calculation outweighs the economic cost required for its calculation.

To assess the clarity of the data and indicators, four questions were used; for feasibility, two; and for relevance and cost-effectiveness, one in each case. Each question had an associated Likert scale with five possible responses, with a specific value assigned to each (for more information, see the Annex), as presented below:

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Table 3 presents a general summary of the key data assessments for each of the attributes. As can be seen, the best-rated attribute was thematic relevance, with a value of 4.5, while clarity had a value of 4.3, economy of 4.2, and feasibility of 3.3. The relatively low value for feasibility is explained by the fact that calculating the value of several indicators requires the design of new representative surveys or the creation of new regulations, and therefore, additional budgetary resources from governments or the implementation of institutional processes for creating new regulations.

¹ Consejo Iberoamericano del Deporte. (2025). *The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development Methodology for Evaluating the Quality of the Indicators*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15191277>

Table 3. *Technical assessment of key data by the countries participating in the pilot (the minimum average value is 1 and the maximum is 5)*

Key Data Points	C	F	PT	E	AVG
1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	5.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	4.5
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	3.7	3.2	3.0	5.0	3.7
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	5.0	3.2	5.0	4.0	4.3
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	3.5	4.0	5.0	3.0	3.9
Average value for the attribute	4.3	3.3	4.5	4.2	

Note: C = Clarity; F = Feasibility; PT = Thematic Relevance; E = Economy; AVG = Average Value; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods of the indicators described in their technical data sheets.

Specifically, the assessment of the feasibility of data point two by Peru (see statistical appendix) is unclear because the information sources for establishing the governmental level of the governing body for sports are easily accessible. In other words, it is simple to find the governmental level of the national sports entity in national regulations. This may be due to confusion between establishing the data point and generating regulations. Similarly, in the assessment of the economic viability of data point four for Peru, the concept of economic viability may not have been well understood, as the argument for its rating (“There are no instruments to measure the contribution of sport to the SDG”) is not related to the assessment of whether, despite this lack, it is worthwhile to invest in generating information sources for its calculation, something that is otherwise quite simple.

Regarding the overall assessment of the key data points (average value of the four attributes), the best-rated was data point one concerning whether “There is a recent national survey on sports practice and physical activity disaggregated by gender and age groups” (value of 4.5). In contrast, the lowest-scoring indicator was four, regarding whether “Legal frameworks exist to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity” (3.9).

On the other hand, Table 4 presents a general summary of the indicators' scores. As with the key data, the worst-scoring attribute of the indicators was feasibility (3.7), while clarity and cost-effectiveness were the best-scoring attributes (4.7 each). Again, the low feasibility score is explained by the fact that calculating the value of several indicators requires designing new representative surveys or satellite accounts, and therefore, investing additional budgetary resources by governments, which can be somewhat restrictive.

Regarding the assessment of the indicators (average value of the four attributes), the low value of indicators 11: “Disability gap in the percentage of the population sufficiently physically active” (value of 3.7) and 12: “Percentage of government programs that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence” (value of 3.6) stands out, which is basically explained by the lack of information sources for their calculation and the need to invest in new surveys or accounting information systems for their calculation.

Table 4. *Technical assessment of the indicators by the countries participating in the pilot (the minimum average value is 1 and the maximum is 5)*

Indicators	C	F	PT	E	AVG
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity.	5.0	3.5	5.0	4.0	4.4
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	4.7	3.7	4.5	4.5	4.3
3. Percentage of the population sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age.	4.4	4.0	3.5	5.0	4.2
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity.	4.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	4.2
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	5.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	4.5
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	4.5	2.2	4.5	5.0	4.0
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	4.7	5.0	5.0	5.0	4.9
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old	5.0	2.0	3.5	5.0	3.9
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	5.0	4.5	5.0	5.0	4.9
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	4.5	1.5	4.5	4.5	3.7
12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	4.4	2.0	4.0	4.0	3.6
Average Value for the attribute	4.7	3.3	4.6	4.7	

Note: C = Clarity; F = Feasibility; PT = Thematic Relevance; E = Economy; AVG = Average Value; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods of the indicators described in their technical data sheets.

Specifically, regarding the indicators, Indicator 4 received the lowest average rating. This is mainly due to the technical complexity of its calculation, even though it is generated by a source external to the participating countries; that is, the countries are not required to calculate it.

Based on the results of the technical assessment, it can be concluded that Peru's ratings were consistently lower than Colombia's. This can be explained in some cases by a lack of information from the country, but also by the lower technical capacity of the working groups to understand the assessment criteria. The latter could be addressed with more training for the countries' technical teams, although this would require increasing the human, financial, and time resources of the Consortium and the participating countries.

III. Status of the operational processes for generating indicators

Operational processes refer to the activities, work mechanisms, and responsibilities of the actors involved in generating information sources, estimating the value of data and indicators, and institutionally validating the reports and documents generated.

The most significant findings regarding the status of operational processes in the countries are presented below:

I. Wide variability in operational processes across countries: Although countries share high institutional similarities, significant differences are observed in the administrative and government accounting categories associated with indicator generation, which translates into challenges for ensuring the full comparability of indicators in the region.

II. Limited documentation of operational processes for generating indicators: In general, there is limited documentation on the traceability for generating the information required by the indicators, as well as on the actors responsible for this. This situation makes it difficult to identify the pathways for producing information and for sharing and managing knowledge.

III. Limited reliable, systematized, and up-to-date sources of information: Partly related to the lack of documentation of operational processes, but also to the lack of financial and human resources and training, there are not enough sources of information to generate all the indicators.

IV. Methodological documents from surveys with limited public access: It was found that no country makes the microdata from the surveys easily and directly available to the public, which greatly hinders their external validation and use by experts to develop related statistical analyses.

V. Insufficient specialized technical staff for generating indicators: One of the most significant obstacles to making adequate progress in the implementation of the pilot was the insufficient technical staff in the countries, especially in Peru, to meet the established time commitments for carrying out the pilot.

VI. Technical staff with low job stability: Very low job stability was observed among the staff specialized in generating indicators and in monitoring and evaluating the impact of sport and physical activity on development. This means that the countries have difficulty consolidating capacities and learning, as well as slowing down the implementation of the indicators and requiring greater support from the consortium's technical team.

VII. Areas of opportunity to improve institutional coordination for information generation: a certain level of fragmentation was observed in the availability of information within countries. In other words, it would be necessary to improve coordination between different sectors to ensure that the information collected is complete and systematic.

IV. Lessons Learned

Lessons learned refer to general situations observed during the pilot that are essential to understand and transform into actions to improve the implementation of the indicators. The most relevant lessons identified are presented below:

- **Given the institutional, administrative, and technical heterogeneity of the countries in the region, establishing precisely comparable indicators across countries is difficult in the short term.** However, the pilot project has identified areas of opportunity for conceptual unification, such as surveys with similar target populations and exercises in statistical or administrative standardization.
- **Countries have different institutional, technical, and budgetary capacities, which are necessarily reflected in the level of indicator implementation.** Therefore, at least in the short term, significant variability in indicator implementation is expected among countries, with many requiring international support to implement several indicators.
- **Some indicators cannot be implemented in the short term without additional budgetary resources.** This is particularly relevant for indicators requiring representative surveys with gender disaggregation or representative surveys of people with disabilities, school statistics, or new budget records.
- **It is essential to have more specialized technical personnel in the countries.** The technical level of the countries' working groups is reflected in their ability to adequately understand the methodologies and basic concepts, evaluate the attributes of the indicators, and establish their value.
- **Expand and improve the training of the countries' technical teams:** in some cases, significant technical limitations were observed in understanding and operationalizing the indicators.
- **Need to involve academia: the capacity to measure and monitor government policies can be substantially improved through partnerships with academia or specialized research centers.** In addition to their benefits for knowledge generation, such partnerships ensure a degree of continuity in information generation and indicator monitoring. Although involving academia was set as an objective at the beginning of the pilot, its participation was very limited in practice.
- **Opportunities for improvement in the pilot methodology:** during the course of the pilot, relevant contributions emerged for improving the methodology and operational tools. In general, it seems advisable to reduce the number of questions used to assess the clarity of the indicators, as well as to clearly distinguish between the countries' capacity to generate statistical information and their capacity to meet certain indicator targets.

V. General Recommendations

Based on the lessons learned, the following recommendations are made to improve the implementation of the indicators:

- **Ensure that the countries' technical teams have the necessary technical expertise and the time available to implement the indicators.** Specifically, they need the ability to interpret methodologies, understand basic statistical concepts, public sector budget categories, work online, and analyze and formulate public policies for sport and physical activity.
- **Strengthen the technical expertise of the consortium's consulting team.** To advance the pilot implementation more thoroughly and quickly, support the countries, and achieve greater comparability of the indicators, specialized profiles in statistical analysis and public sector budget categories are required.
- **Partner with a local university for indicator development.** Collaboration with a local university, which possesses contextual knowledge and available time, would be extremely helpful in strengthening the countries' technical and operational response capacities. In phases one and two of the pilot, there was very little support from universities for indicator development.
- **Formalize long-term strategic partnerships.** The creation of medium- and long-term agreements between the institutions participating in the Consortium and between the Consortium and the countries would strengthen the administrative and financial certainty of the indicators' implementation.
- **Translating the countries' political commitment into concrete operational actions.** It is important to find mechanisms through which the countries' political commitment translates into greater resources for the pilot project's implementation and the strengthening of the technical teams.
- **Sharing experiences and knowledge among countries.** It would be important to link national initiatives with international standards, ensuring the alignment of national policies with best practices.
- **Strengthening the participatory approach to the methodologies.** It is necessary to expand the participatory process involving countries and academic experts to strengthen the working methodologies and operational implementation tools.
- **International funding for some indicators.** It is necessary to seek partnerships with international financial institutions focused on financing capacity building for monitoring and evaluating the impact of sport on sustainable development.

VI. Specific recommendations for indicators that could not be implemented and their potential funding

As stated above in the document, one of the most important constraints to generating indicators is the lack of sufficient budget in the governments of the region to finance the creation of the information sources needed to calculate them.

This section identifies the areas with the greatest need for government financing to implement the indicators. A first area of financing is related to the generation of national surveys to meet: data point one, on whether “there is a national survey no more than five years old on sports practice and physical activity disaggregated by gender and age groups”; data point three, on the “percentage of the population that is sufficiently physically active, disaggregated by gender and age”; and indicator nine on the “percentage of the gender gap in the sufficiently physically active population.” This also includes the financing required to conduct surveys or a school census to calculate indicator five on the “percentage of primary and secondary schools that provide the minimum required number of minutes of physical education.”

Table 5 describes the key data and indicators that could not be implemented or whose values could not be estimated due to the lack of an information source that requires significant financing. As can be observed, columns three and four provide a brief explanation of the justification and specific purpose of the financing.

A second area of financing relates to institutional and operational strengthening to generate the indicators, specifically: training, preparation of studies and publications, and international cooperation schemes and exchanges of experience. These aspects are described in greater detail below.

- **Training:** It is necessary to expand and improve the training of technical teams on aspects of measurement and the design of evaluation and monitoring indicators. This training requires basic knowledge of causality, impact measurement, and the design of representative probabilistic surveys, as well as their application to the field of sport and physical activity.
- **Studies and publications:** To create a positive environment conducive to investment in sport and physical activity, it is necessary to disseminate the enormous impact that sport has on sustainable development and even consider its study as a dimension of development itself. For this, it is essential to disseminate achievements, progress, and challenges through public policy documents or academic studies, for whose preparation and dissemination funding is needed.
- **International cooperation:** As documented in the pilot project, countries can arrive at creative solutions to certain challenges or problems from their own perspectives and contexts, solutions that would be important for other countries to be aware of. Similarly, various dimensions of measuring sport and physical activity are still the subject of relevant conceptual discussions, which demands constant interaction and debate between government and academic specialists to reach a consensus. Therefore, it is important to have sufficient funds to finance international cooperation events and exchanges of experiences between specialists and decision-makers.

Table 5. Indicators with total or partial absence of information sources eligible for funding

Key Data or Indicator	Country	Proposal	Explanation
D.1. A national survey on sports participation and physical activity, broken down by gender and age group, is available within the last five years.	Colombia and Peru	Justification	The data has a partial fulfillment value because the surveys are more than 5 years old and lack sufficient disaggregation by age and sex or gender.
		Route for country	Formation of an inter-institutional working group to identify the technical and financial requirements for conducting more disaggregated and periodic surveys.
		Object of financing	Achieve representative national surveys for people under 18, aged 18 to 64, and over 65, disaggregated by sex or gender, with publicly available microdata.
I.2. Percentage contribution of sports and physical activity to the Gross Domestic Product	Peru	Justification	This indicator has no value due to the absence of a satellite account on sport and physical activity or a system of national accounts that allows for a precise, reliable, and disaggregated estimate of the sector's contribution to Gross Domestic Product.
		Route for country	Formation of an inter-institutional working group to identify the technical and financial requirements for designing a satellite account.
		Object of financing	Creation of a satellite account for sport and physical activity, as its implementation typically involves considerable financial and technical challenges for the national governing bodies of sport and physical activity in the region.
I.5. Percentage of primary and secondary schools that provide the minimum number of minutes of physical education	Colombia and Peru	Justification	Indicator without value due to the lack of an administrative census or representative survey that would allow for its calculation.
		Route for country	Establish the necessary mechanisms to conduct an administrative census or a representative national survey.
		Object of financing	Administrative census or a representative national survey.

I.11. Percentage in the disability gap in the physically sufficiently active population	Colombia and Peru	Justification	Indicator with no value because there is no representative survey on sport and physical activity for people with disabilities.
		Route for country	Integration of an interdisciplinary working group to define concepts and measurements to be included in the representative survey.
		Object of financing	Representative survey on sport and physical activity for people with disabilities, disaggregated by age and gender or sex, and less than five years old.

Annex. Detailed technical assessment of key data and indicators

Table 1A. Detailed assessment by countries of the clarity of key data at the start of the pilot* (maximum average value is 5 and minimum is 1)

Question	Country	Value for each Key Data Point				
		1	2	3	4	AVG
The data name is self-explanatory (it correctly expresses the unit of measurement, does not use acronyms, or defines them precisely).	COL	5	5	5	5	5
	PER	5	5	5	4	4.7
The method for calculating the data is consistent with its name.	COL	5	5	5	5	5
	PER	5	1	5	1	3
The data validation criteria are clear and self-explanatory.	COL	5	5	5	5	5
	PER	5	1	5	1	3
Average for each Key Data Point		5.0	3.7	5.0	3.5	

Note: AVG = Average value; 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the data presented in this document, as well as into the calculation methods described in their technical data sheets.

Table 2A. Detailed assessment by countries of the feasibility of key data at the start of the pilot* (maximum average value is 5 and minimum is 1)

Question	Country	Value for each Key Data Point				
		1	2	3	4	AVG
Currently, the data sources for calculating the indicator are available from the national sports authority or official government sources.	COL	5	5	3	5	4.5
	PER	5	1	5	5	4
If the data sources for calculating the indicator are currently unavailable or outdated, it would be possible to generate them without requiring extraordinary human or material resources from the government.	COL	1	5	4	5	3.7
	PER	1	2	1	1	1.2
Average for each Key Data Point		3.0	3.2	3.2	4.0	

Note: AVG = Average value; 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the data presented in this document, as well as into the calculation methods described in their technical data sheets.

Table 3A. Detailed assessment by countries of the thematic relevance of key data at the start of the pilot* (the maximum average value is 5 and the minimum is 1)

Question	Country	Value for each Key Data Point				
		1	2	3	4	AVG
The data addresses a higher-order theme linked to policy or program objectives for sport, physical activity, or physical education.	COL	5	1	5	5	4
	PER	5	5	5	5	5
Average for each Key Data Point		5.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	

Note: AVG = Average value; 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the data presented in this document, as well as into the calculation methods described in their technical data sheets.

Table 4A. Detailed assessment of countries on the economy of key data at the start of the pilot* (maximum average value is 5 and minimum is 1)

Question	Country	Value for each Key Data Point				
		1	2	3	4	AVG
The usefulness of the data in measuring the contribution of sport, physical education or physical education to the achievement of a sustainable development goal justifies the cost or effort associated with its calculation.	COL	5	5	5	5	5
	PER	5	5	3	1	3.5
Average for each Key Data Point		5.0	5.0	4.0	3.0	

Note: AVG = Average value; 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the data presented in this document, as well as into the calculation methods described in their technical data sheets.

Table 5A. Detailed assessment by countries of the clarity of the indicators at the start of the pilot* (the maximum average value is 5 and the minimum is 1)

Question	Country	Value for each Indicator												AVG
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
The indicator's name is self-explanatory (it correctly expresses the unit of measurement, does not use acronyms, or defines them precisely).	COL	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4.9
	PER	5	2	4	2	Nd	Nd	4	4	5	Nd	4	4	3.7
The indicator's definition is consistent with its name.	COL	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.0
	PER	5	5	4	2	Nd	Nd	4	4	5	Nd	4	4	4.1
The indicator's definition is consistent with its calculation formula.	COL	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.0
	PER	5	5	2	5	Nd	Nd	4	5	5	Nd	4	4	4.3
The units of measurement for the variables in the indicator's calculation formula are consistent.	COL	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5.0
	PER	5	5	5	3	Nd	Nd	4	5	5	Nd	4	4	4.4
Average for each Indicator		5.0	4.7	4.4	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.5	4.7	5.0	5.0	4.5	4.4	

Note: AVG = Average value; 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods of the indicators described in their technical data sheets.

Table 6A. Detailed assessment by countries of the feasibility of the indicators at the start of the pilot* (the maximum average value is 5 and the minimum is 1)

Question	Country	Value for each Indicator												AVG
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Currently, the data sources for calculating the indicator are available from the national sports authority or official government sources.	COL	5	5	5	5	2	5	2	5	5	4	1	2	3.8
	PER	5	2	5	1	Nd	Nd	2	5	1	Nd	2	2	2.8
If the data sources for calculating the indicator are currently unavailable or outdated, it would be possible to generate them without requiring extraordinary human or material resources from the government.	COL	3	3	5	5	4	5	3	5	1	5	1	2	3.5
	PER	1	2	1	1	Nd	Nd	2	Nd	1	Nd	2	2	1.3
Average for each Indicator		3.5	3.7	4.0	3.0	3.0	5.0	2.2	5.0	2.0	4.5	1.5	2.0	

Note: AVG = Average value; 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods of the indicators described in their technical data sheets.

Table 7A. Detailed assessment by countries of the thematic relevance of the indicators at the start of the pilot* (the maximum average value is 5 and the minimum is 1)

Question	Country	Value for each Indicator												AVG
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
The indicator addresses a higher-order theme linked to policy or program objectives for sport, physical activity, or physical education.	COL	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	4	4.8
	PER	5	4	2	5	Nd	Nd	5	5	2	Nd	4	4	4.0
Average for each Indicator		5.0	4.5	3.5	5.0	5.0	5.0	4.5	5.0	3.5	5.0	4.5	4.0	

Note: AVG = Average value; 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods of the indicators described in their technical data sheets.

Table 8A. Detailed assessment of countries on the economy of the indicators at the start of the pilot* (the maximum average value is 5 and the minimum is 1)

Question	Country	Value for each Indicator												AVG
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
The usefulness of the indicator in measuring the contribution of sport, physical education or physical education to the achievement of a sustainable development goal justifies the cost or effort associated with its calculation.	COL	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4.9
	PER	3	4	5	5	Nd	Nd	5	5	5	Nd	4	4	4.5
Average for each Indicator		4.0	4.5	5.0	4.5	4.0								

Note: AVG = Average value; 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neither agree nor disagree; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly agree; * Most of the observations or recommendations identified have already been incorporated into the wording of the indicators presented in this document, as well as the calculation methods of the indicators described in their technical data sheets.